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First steps towards improving measurement of interfacial segregation in SEM

Aluminium layers of different thicknesses deposited onto graphite discs by thermal evaporation were investigated first individually in top-down geometry and results compared to depth profiling experiments as well as to Monte Carlo simulations. Then all the individual samples were glued together into one stack that was investigated in cross-section in an FEI Quanta 250 with Ametek EDAX Octane Elite 55 SDD. Maps of Al and C X-rays have been acquired at different acceleration voltages and the results quantified using a window ratio and slope fitting technique originally developed for (S)TEM [1].

Fig. 1: SEM-EDXS maps of Al (top left) and C (top right) and profiles of nom. 10nm layer (5kV, 50μm aperture, spot size 5, ~7.2nA). Sampling: 101.2 nm/pixel.

Preliminary results show a reasonable agreement between results from the traditional integration of compositional profiles with those obtained by the new slope fitting procedure. The detection limits are hard to estimate as they seem to be governed by the high interface roughness due to the initial porosity of the graphite target, rather than by the SEM-EDXS methodology itself, however, it is clear that precision and sensitivity lie well below the sampling or spatial resolution limits.

nominal Al deposition [nm]	Dektak [nm]	EDXS Al/C ratio top-down	t [nm] from EDXS fit to Casino v2.42 [2]	t [nm] from x-sectional Al/C profile	t [nm] from inverse slope of C/AI windows
500	449±106	53.78	210.0±10		
100	117±34	4.712	121.3±0.6		
10	12±8	0.0408	9.8±2.2	24±4	25±2
1	—	0.0102	3.1±0.6		
1	—	0.0021	0.7±0.4		

References:

- [1] T. Walther. *J Microscopy* 223:2 (2006) 165-170
- [2] D. Drouin, A. Real Couture, D. Joly, X. Tastet, V. Aimez, R. Gauvin. *Scanning* 29 (2007) 92-101